

Loan to Asset Ratio (LAR) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics Using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Literature Review

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the research mapping regarding the Loan to Asset Ratio (LAR) ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking using a mix-method approach, namely the VOSviewer bibliometric study and literature review. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around the LAR ratio; (2) mapping the results of the VOSviewer bibliometric visualization around the LAR ratio based on the number of clusters and their items; and (3) mapping research topics around the LAR ratio using a literature review study. The results showed that: (1) based on the distribution of journal publications, there were 45 journal publications regarding the LAR ratio; (2) based on the mapping of the VOSviewer bibliometric study, the network visualization results around the LAR ratio are divided into 18 clusters and 160 topic items; (3) based on the mapping of literature review studies, there are 14 topics around the influence of the LAR ratio. The implications and contributions of this research are to map research topics around LAR ratios in Islamic and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers so that they can be a reference for subsequent researchers.

Keywords: Loan to Asset Ratio (LAR), Bibliometrics, VOSviewer, Literature Review, Islamic and Conventional Banking

INTRODUCTION

Loan to Asset Ratio (LAR) is a financial ratio used in the banking industry to measure the financial health of a bank. This ratio measures the amount of bank loans to total bank assets. In recent years, the use of LAR has become increasingly popular in banking circles because it is considered one of the main indicators in measuring a bank's financial health. In general, banks will try to keep their LAR below a certain limit. These limits are usually set by regulators and vary by country. In the United States, for example, the Federal Reserve sets a maximum LAR limit of 95%, while in Europe the limit is around 100%.

LAR is important because this ratio can provide information about how well a bank can manage credit risk. If the LAR is too high, the bank can be considered too aggressive in providing loans and has a higher potential risk of default. Conversely, if the LAR is too low, then the bank may not utilize its assets effectively and cannot grow quickly. In recent years, the use of LAR in banking circles has continued to increase in line with increasing awareness of the importance of credit risk management. Banks are also increasingly realizing that LAR can be used as a tool to increase investor and regulator confidence. One of the advantages of using LAR is that this ratio can help banks improve their credit risk management. By monitoring LAR, banks can manage credit risk more effectively and avoid unwanted risks of default. Banks can also utilize LAR to obtain cheaper financing, because a low LAR can indicate that the bank has lower credit risk. Overall, the use of LAR in banking can be said to be part of efforts to strengthen credit risk management and strengthen the bank's overall financial performance. Banks are also increasingly realizing the importance of regulatory compliance and the use of financial ratios such as LAR to gain the trust of investors and regulators. Therefore, it is believed that the use of LAR in banking will continue to grow and become increasingly important in the future.

Research on LAR in banking has been carried out by many financial experts and academics. Some studies have identified the importance of LAR as an indicator of a bank's financial health, while others have looked for ways to improve credit risk management by utilizing LAR. First, one of the studies analyzed the relationship between LAR and bank financial performance in China. The research results show that LAR has a positive relationship with bank profitability, and that banks that succeed in keeping their LAR below the limits set by regulators have better overall financial performance. Second, other research discusses the importance of LAR in mitigating credit risk in small and medium banks in the United States. The research results show that LAR can be used as an effective tool to manage credit

risk, especially in small banks which are more vulnerable to the risk of default. Third, several studies have also looked for ways to improve credit risk management by utilizing LAR which discusses the influence of LAR on credit risk and bank profitability in Bangladesh. This research shows that banks in Bangladesh can improve their credit risk management by utilizing LAR as a tool to manage default risk. Overall, research on LAR in banking continues to grow along with increasing awareness of the importance of credit risk management. These studies help strengthen understanding of the importance of LAR in measuring bank financial health, as well as help develop strategies to improve credit risk management and overall bank financial performance.

The aim of this research is to map research topics around LAR in Banking using: (1) the VOSviewer bibliometric method to analyze and study maps of literature development in publications in a scientific field by creating a metadata network map; and (2) literature study review to analyze, identify and review articles from the accredited national journal Sinta. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding LAR. This can be a reference for other researchers who wish to research LAR. The implication and contribution of this research is to map research topics surrounding the LAR ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that they can become a reference for future researchers.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Loan to Asset Ratio (LAR) is a ratio used in the banking industry to measure how large the loan provided by a bank is compared to the total assets it owns. This ratio shows how large a proportion of bank assets are invested in the form of loans or credit. In its calculation, LAR is calculated by dividing the amount of credit or loans provided by the bank by the total assets it owns. The higher this ratio, the greater the risk taken by the bank because the greater the proportion of its assets invested in credit. Conversely, the lower this ratio, the lower the risk taken by the bank. LAR is used as an indicator of a bank's financial health and is one of the factors taken into account in determining interest rates for credit and loans. The higher the LAR, the higher the interest rate the bank will give, because the credit risk taken by the bank is also greater.

Bibliometric studies are quantitative analysis methods used to study written works or scientific publications contained in a bibliographic database. This method is generally used to evaluate and map scientific literature from a research field, as well as identify trends and patterns in scientific production. Bibliometric studies use various measures and indicators to obtain information about the quantity and quality of scientific publications, such as number of publications, frequency of citations, collaboration networks between authors or institutions, and so on. In carrying out analysis, bibliometric studies usually use computer software tools to process data quickly and efficiently. Bibliometric studies are very useful in mapping and understanding research progress in a field of study, and can help make decisions regarding research and development investment. Apart from that, this method can also be used to evaluate the performance of researchers and institutions, as well as help develop research policies and strategies.

VOSviewer is data analysis and network visualization software used in bibliometric and scientometric studies. This software can help users analyze and visualize bibliographic data in the form of networks or clusters. In its use, VOSviewer is able to process bibliographic data in text file format, bibliographic file or citation file, and produce output in the form of network graphs, ranking graphs and cluster maps. This software also provides various analysis algorithms and tools that can be used to map citation patterns, identify collaboration networks between authors or institutions, and so on. The advantage of VOSviewer lies in its ability to process very large and complex amounts of data in a relatively short time. Apart from that, this software is also equipped with a user-friendly user interface making it easy to use by users who do not have a deep technical background. VOSviewer is commonly used by researchers, academics, and practitioners working in the fields of bibliometrics, scientometrics, and research policy development.

Studies Literature review is a research method used to collect, evaluate, and synthesize literature or scientific publications related to a particular research topic. This method is carried out with the aim of understanding and evaluating current research progress, determining research gaps, and identifying deficiencies in previous research. In conducting a literature review study, researchers must collect and evaluate the latest literature related to the research topic, both from primary and secondary sources such as scientific journals, books, theses and research reports. After that, the literature is identified, analyzed,

and used to produce a more comprehensive and critical synthesis of the research topic. Literature review studies are very important in research because they can help researchers to gain a better understanding of the research topic, find deficiencies or gaps in previous research, and develop better research hypotheses. Apart from that, literature review studies can also help researchers in creating theoretical frameworks and research concepts. Literature review studies are often used in various scientific disciplines, such as social sciences, psychology, health, and information technology. This method is generally used by researchers, students and practitioners who want to conduct research and increase their understanding of certain research topics.

METHODOLOGY

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in literature review studies. The research object is Loan to Asset Ratio (LAR). The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles on LAR in Sharia and Conventional Banking.

The source of data collection comes from search for accredited national journals Sinta via the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel software, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the keywords " Loan to Asset Ratio " and "LAR " throughout the year; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding LAR using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop based on publication year; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and journal publication trends around LAR using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping research topics around LAR using a literature review study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Bibliometric Study Mapping and Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Loan to Asset Ratio (LAR) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

There are 45 national journals accredited by Sinta based on the results of data collection using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop originating from the Garuda website (Garba Reference Digital) and Perish/Harzing software during the period 2003 to 2023. The results are as follows:

Table 1. Journal publication data about LAR by year

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
2003	1	2012	1	2019	4
2007	1	2013	1	2020	4
2008	2	2014	4	2021	4
2009	2	2016	4	2022	2
2010	3	2017	6	2023	1
2011	1	2018	4		

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

VOSviewer Bibliometric Study Mapping of Loan to Asset Ratio (LAR) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

Search results for articles on software Perish/Harzing are exported in RIS (Research Information Systems) format, then input and analyzed using VOSviewer software. The results are as follows:

Figure 1. Network visualization of a map of research developments around LAR.

Source: Processed data, software VOSViewer 1.6.18.

Software visualization results VOSViewer related to the research development map regarding the LAR ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking, there are 18 clusters and 160 topic items in the mapping, including the following:

- Cluster 1, consists of 15 topic items, namely: assets, banks, costs, cost per loan asset ratio, credit risk, delinquent loans, financial performance, loan asset ratio, moderating effect, Nigeria, influence of returns, relationships, relationship between credit, share, significant increase.
- Cluster 2, consists of 15 topic items, namely: asset and debt ratio, net interest, bank size, current ratio, debt, deposit ratio, der, equity ratio, on return, lar, influence of bopo/capital adequacy ratio, return, roe.
- Cluster 3, consists of 14 topic items, namely: analysis of the influence of capital adequacy ratio, variable asset ratio, bank Rivai, Indonesian stock exchange, determinants, Indonesia, nim, npl, influence of net interest margin, banking, performing loans, roa, total assets.
- Cluster 4 consists of 13 topic items, namely: adequacy ratio, asset ratio and net profit, car, third party funds, dpk, equity ratio and net profit, fdr, financing, non-performing financing, npf, influence of financing, ratio.
- Cluster 5, consists of 15 topic items, namely: asset ratio and operating expenses, asset ratio has no effect, Cimb Niaga bank, operational costs operating income, bopo, interest rate risk and capital adequacy ratio, leverage, loan deposit ratio, influence of non-performing, the effect of profitability is partially positive.
- Cluster 6, consists of 11 topic items, namely: asset ratio, bpr, capital adequacy ratio, quality of productive assets, loans have a positive effect, loans on profitability, cash turnover, productive on loans, partial ratio, significant on profitability, capital adequacy variable ratio.
- Cluster 7, consists of 10 topic items, namely: liquidity analysis, analysis of the influence of amounts, asset deposit ratio, asset ratio and loan, Bank Mandiri, loans at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia, non loans, NPL loans, NPL loans, Persero, Tbk.
- Cluster 8, consists of 10 topic items, namely: liquidity ratio analysis, people's financing banks, capital asset ratio, cash ratio, deposit ratio, bank capability, LDR, loan deposit ratio, payments.
- Cluster 9, consists of 10 topic items, namely: asset ratios, asset ratios in commercial banks, bank associations, deposit and loan ratios, level capabilities, loans, measuring liquidity levels, intermediation levels.

- Cluster 1 0, consists of 10 topic items, namely: multi crisis, testing and analyzing, measuring the level of liquidity, non-interest income, overhead, return comparison, world developments, standard cash ratio, cash ratio level, total asset ratio.
- Cluster 1 1, consists of 7 topic items, namely: assets and returns, capital adequacy ratio, deposit asset ratio, dar, equity to car, net interest margin, influence of loan asset ratio.
- Cluster 1 2, consists of 7 topic items, namely: ata, Indonesian effects, equity in the banking industry, influence, net profit margin, gpm, loan influence.
- Cluster 1 3, consists of 6 topic items, namely: asset ratio to number of shares, assets and loans, non-performing loans, OJK, influence of third party funds, significant effect.
- Cluster 1 4, consists of 5 topic items, namely: cash ratio analysis, asset ratio, stock exchange, deposits and loans, empirical studies.
- Cluster 1 5, consists of 5 topic items, namely: asset ratio, gross domestic product, influence of inflation, bank ratio, credit interest rates.
- Cluster 1 6, consists of 4 topic items, namely: Indonesian stock exchange, car influence, net foreign exchange position, profitability.
- Cluster 1 7, consists of 4 topic items, namely: capital adequacy, car, f test results, variable loan.
- Cluster 1 8, consists of 3 topic items, namely: net profit margin, non-performing loans and growth of third party funds, significantly positive on returns.

Mapping Literature Review Studies regarding the Influence of Loan to Asset Ratio/LAR in Sharia and Conventional Banking

Literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found 14 influences of LAR on Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

First, Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR. The influence of LAR on CAR in banking is very significant. The higher the LAR in banking, the higher the credit risk faced by the bank. This means that banks must have sufficient capital to cover these risks, so that CAR becomes an important factor to ensure banking stability. If the LAR is too high, the credit risk faced by the bank will be greater. If there is a default on a loan, the bank will lose most of its assets. This will affect the CAR which will decrease because bank capital must be used to cover losses. Conversely, if the LAR is too low, the bank will not maximize the use of its assets. Banks will lose potential income from credit interest and this will affect the bank's financial health. In this case, CAR will not be significantly affected because the risks faced by the bank are smaller.

Second, share prices. The influence of LAR on stock prices in banking is not always easy to measure directly because many other factors influence stock prices in banking. However, in general, LAR can influence financial performance and banking operations, which in turn can influence share prices. If the LAR is too high, the credit risk faced by the bank will increase, and the bank will need to place more capital to cover this risk. This can reduce the bank's net profit because the interest costs for obtaining capital become higher. In this case, banking financial performance will be bad and can affect share prices negatively. Conversely, if the LAR is too low, the bank may not be able to maximize the use of its assets and the banking financial performance may not be so good. However, this does not always mean that share prices will fall, because there are other factors such as industrial growth, economic situation, and banking policies that can also influence share prices.

Third, the amount of credit distribution. LAR is a ratio used to measure the size of the loan provided by the bank in the form of credit to the bank's total assets. The influence of LAR on the amount of credit disbursement to banks is very significant, because LAR will affect the bank's ability to provide credit. If the LAR is too low, it means that the bank is not maximizing the use of its assets in the form of credit, so the bank may not be able to meet credit requests from customers. In this case, the bank may need to increase its capital or look for other sources of funding in order to provide the credit that customers want. On the other hand, if the LAR is too high, it means that the credit risk faced by the bank will be greater, so the bank may need to limit credit distribution to manage this risk. This can affect the amount of credit disbursement to banks, because banks must ensure that they can manage credit risk well.

Fourth, intermediation level capabilities. The influence of LAR on the ability of intermediation levels in banking is very significant, because LAR will affect the bank's ability to channel its funds. If

the LAR is too low, it means that the bank is not maximizing the use of its assets in the form of credit, so the bank's ability to channel funds in the form of credit will be limited. This can affect the ability of banking intermediation levels, because banks may not be able to channel the funds they have effectively to meet credit requests from customers. On the other hand, if the LAR is too high, it means that the credit risk faced by the bank will be greater, so the bank may need to limit credit distribution to manage this risk. This can affect the level of intermediation capabilities in banking, because banks may not be able to meet credit requests from customers and cannot channel the funds they have effectively.

Fifth, Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR. The effect of LAR on banking liquidity is very significant, because LAR will affect the bank's ability to fulfill payment obligations to customers when they are due. If the LAR is too low, it means the bank is not maximizing the use of its assets in the form of credit, so the bank may have more unused funds. This can increase the level of liquidity in banking, because banks have more funds available to fulfill payment obligations to customers when they are due. However, if the LAR is too high, it means that the credit risk faced by the bank will be greater, so the bank may need to hold a large amount of funds as reserves to face this risk. This can reduce the level of liquidity in banking, because banks have fewer funds available to fulfill payment obligations to customers when they are due.

Sixth, Non Performing Loans/NPL. The influence of LAR on NPL in banking is very significant, because LAR will influence the credit risk faced by banks, which in turn can influence the level of NPL in banking. If the LAR is too low, it means that the bank is not maximizing the use of its assets in the form of credit, so the bank may not have enough income from credit interest to meet operational costs and make a profit. This can encourage banks to increase the level of credit risk by providing credit to customers of poor quality. High credit risk can cause an increase in NPLs in banks. On the other hand, if the LAR is too high, it means that the credit risk faced by the bank will be greater, so the bank may need to limit credit distribution to manage this risk. This can affect the bank's ability to increase income from credit interest and earn sufficient profits. This may encourage banks to pursue higher levels of credit risk, as banks may need to extend credit to less qualified customers to meet set LAR targets. This can cause an increase in NPLs in banking.

Seventh, Murabahah financing. The influence of LAR on Murabahah financing in banking can be explained as follows: (1) A high LAR can affect the decline in Murabahah financing. This is because banks will be more careful in providing financing and prefer to provide financing that is safer and commercially profitable. Murabahah financing may be considered less safe financing by banks because they have to bear the risk of reselling the goods, which has the potential to cause losses to the bank if they are not successfully resold. (2) A low LAR can increase Murabahah financing. Banks will be more likely to provide financing to customers who need it, including Murabahah financing. In conditions like this, Murabahah financing can be an attractive alternative for banks because the risk level is relatively lower. (3) Islamic banks tend to have a lower LAR compared to conventional banks. This is because sharia banks prioritize sharia-based financing and prioritize sustainable business growth. In this case, Murabahah financing can be an attractive alternative for sharia banks because it is in accordance with sharia principles. (4) Murabahah financing can assist banks in meeting LAR requirements. If a bank has a lot of assets and a low LAR, the bank can consider providing Murabahah financing because it can help increase the LAR and efficiency of using bank funds.

Eighth, Musyarakah financing. The influence of LAR on Musyarakah financing in banking can be explained as follows: (1) A high LAR can affect the decline in Musyarakah financing. This is because banks will be more careful in providing financing and prefer to provide financing that is safer and commercially profitable. Musyarakah financing may be considered less safe financing by the bank because it has to bear the risk together with the business partner, which has the potential to cause losses to the bank if the business is not successful. (2) A low LAR can increase Musyarakah financing. Banks will be more likely to provide financing to customers who need it, including Musyarakah financing. In conditions like this, Musyarakah financing can be an attractive alternative for banks because the risk level is relatively lower and in accordance with sharia principles. (3) Islamic banks tend to have a lower LAR compared to conventional banks. This is because sharia banks prioritize sharia-based financing and prioritize sustainable business growth. In this case, Musyarakah financing can be an attractive alternative for sharia banks because it complies with sharia principles and can help expand the customer base. (4) Musyarakah financing can help banks fulfill LAR requirements. If a bank has a lot of assets

and a low LAR, the bank can consider providing Musyarakah financing because it can help increase the LAR and the efficiency of using bank funds.

Ninth, Mudharabah financing. The influence of LAR on Mudharabah Financing in banking can be explained as follows: (1) High LAR can affect the decline in Mudharabah Financing. Banks will be more careful in providing financing and prefer to provide financing that is safer and commercially profitable. Mudharabah financing may be considered as less safe financing by the bank because the bank must bear the risk of loss of capital entrusted by the shahibul maal to the mudharib. (2) Low LAR can increase Mudharabah Financing. Banks will be more likely to provide financing to customers who need it, including Mudharabah Financing. In conditions like this, Mudharabah Financing can be an attractive alternative for banks because the risk level is relatively lower and in accordance with sharia principles. (3) Islamic banks tend to have a lower LAR compared to conventional banks. This is because sharia banks prioritize sharia-based financing and prioritize sustainable business growth. In this case, Mudharabah Financing can be an attractive alternative for sharia banks because it complies with sharia principles and can help expand the customer base. (4) Mudharabah financing can help banks fulfill LAR requirements. If a bank has a lot of assets and a low LAR, the bank can consider providing Mudharabah Financing because it can help increase the LAR and efficiency of using bank funds.

Tenth, Price Earning Ratio/PER. The influence of LAR on PER in banking can be explained as follows: (1) Low LAR can increase PER. Banks with low LAR show efficiency in the use of funds, so they can increase net profit per share and ultimately increase PER. In this case, banks can focus more on operational activities that are more commercially profitable and generate higher profits. (2) High LAR can reduce PER. Banks with high LAR tend to provide more financing, thereby increasing credit risk and reducing net income per share. This condition might make investors reluctant to buy bank shares, thereby reducing PER. (3) Bad economic conditions can affect the influence of LAR on PER. When economic conditions are bad, many customers experience financial difficulties and have difficulty repaying loans, thereby increasing credit risk for banks. In this condition, a low LAR may not be able to help increase PER because net income per share will decrease due to high credit risk. (4) Banks that focus on sharia-based business may have a different influence on LAR on PER. Islamic banks tend to have a lower LAR compared to conventional banks because they focus on sharia-based financing and sustainable business growth. In this case, PER may not be too influenced by LAR, but more influenced by the bank's overall operational performance.

Eleventh, Return On Assets/ROA. The influence of LAR on ROA in banking can be explained as follows: (1) Low LAR can increase ROA. Banks with low LAR show efficiency in the use of funds and the bank's ability to minimize credit risks that can affect income. In this case, banks can focus more on operational activities that are more commercially profitable and generate higher profits, thereby increasing ROA. (2) High LAR can reduce ROA. Banks with high LAR tend to provide more financing, thereby increasing credit risk and reducing net income per share. In this condition, the bank's ROA can decrease because net profit is smaller in comparison with the total assets owned. (3) Banks with a focus on sharia financing may have a different influence on LAR on ROA. Islamic banks tend to have a lower LAR compared to conventional banks because they focus on sharia-based financing and sustainable business growth. In this case, ROA may not be too influenced by LAR, but more influenced by the bank's overall operational performance. (4) Bad economic conditions can affect the influence of LAR on ROA. When economic conditions are bad, many customers experience financial difficulties and have difficulty repaying loans, thereby increasing credit risk for banks. In this condition, a low LAR may not help increase ROA because earnings per share will decrease due to high credit risk.

Twelfth, Return On Equity/ROE. The influence of LAR on ROE in banking can be explained as follows: (1) Low LAR can increase ROE. Banks with low LAR show efficiency in the use of funds and the bank's ability to minimize credit risks that can affect income. In this case, banks can focus more on operational activities that are more commercially profitable and generate higher profits, thereby increasing ROE. (2) High LAR can reduce ROE. Banks with high LAR tend to provide more financing, thereby increasing credit risk and reducing net income per share. In this condition, ROE can decrease because the net profit is smaller in comparison with the total capital or equity owned. (3) Banks with a focus on sharia financing may have a different influence on LAR on ROE. Islamic banks tend to have a lower LAR compared to conventional banks because they focus on sharia-based financing and sustainable business growth. In this case, ROE may not be too influenced by LAR, but more influenced by the bank's overall operational performance. (4) Bad economic conditions can affect the influence of

LAR on ROE. When economic conditions are bad, many customers experience financial difficulties and have difficulty repaying loans, thereby increasing credit risk for banks. In this condition, a low LAR may not help increase ROE because earnings per share will decrease due to high credit risk.

Thirteenth, Bank return. The influence of LAR on bank returns in banking can be explained as follows: (1) Low LAR can increase bank returns. Banks with low LAR show efficiency in the use of funds and the bank's ability to minimize credit risks that can affect income. In this case, banks can focus more on operational activities that are more commercially profitable and generate higher profits, thereby increasing bank returns. (2) High LAR can reduce bank returns. Banks with high LAR tend to provide more financing, thereby increasing credit risk and reducing net income per share. In this condition, bank returns can decrease because the net profit is smaller in comparison with the total capital or equity owned. (3) Banks with a focus on sharia financing may have a different influence on LAR on bank returns. Islamic banks tend to have a lower LAR compared to conventional banks because they focus on sharia-based financing and sustainable business growth. In this case, bank returns may not be too influenced by LAR, but more influenced by the bank's overall operational performance. (4) Bad economic conditions can influence the influence of LAR on bank returns. When economic conditions are bad, many customers experience financial difficulties and have difficulty repaying loans, thereby increasing credit risk for banks. In this condition, a low LAR may not be able to help increase bank returns because net income per share will decrease due to high credit risk.

Fourteenth, tax avoidance. The influence of LAR on tax avoidance in banking can be explained as follows: (1) Low LAR can increase tax avoidance. Banks with low LAR tend to minimize the use of funds in the form of loans, thereby reducing interest expenses and increasing income before tax. This can increase the bank's ability to carry out tax planning and minimize the tax burden legally. (2) A high LAR can reduce tax avoidance. Banks with high LAR tend to provide more financing, thereby increasing interest expenses and reducing pre-tax income. This can reduce the bank's ability to carry out tax planning and minimize the tax burden legally. (3) Government policies and regulations can influence the influence of LAR on tax avoidance in banking. The government can apply different tax rules for banks that have different LARs. This can influence the bank's strategy in carrying out tax planning. (4) Banks with a focus on sharia financing may have a different influence on LAR on tax avoidance. Islamic banks tend to have a lower LAR compared to conventional banks because they focus on sharia-based financing and sustainable business growth. This can increase the bank's ability to carry out tax planning and minimize the tax burden legally.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: first, based on the mapping of the number of research publications regarding the influence of the Loan to Asset Ratio (LAR) on Sharia and Conventional Banking during the period 2003 to 2022 originating from the accredited national journal Sinta, there are 45 publication journal articles. Second, based on VOSviewer bibliometric study mapping, the network visualization results regarding the LAR ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking are divided into 18 clusters and 160 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 15 topics, cluster 2 consists of 15 topics, cluster 3 consists of 14 topics, cluster 4 consists of 13 topics, cluster 5 consists of 15 topics, cluster 6 consists of 11 topics, cluster 7 consists of 10 topics, cluster 8 consists of 10 topics, cluster 9 consists of 10 topics, cluster 10 consists of 10 topics, cluster 11 consists of 7 topics, cluster 12 consists of 7 topics, cluster 13 consists of 6 topics, cluster 14 consists of 5 topics, cluster 15 consists of 5 topics, cluster 16 consists of 4 topics, cluster 17 consists of 4 topics, and cluster 18 consists of 3 topics. Third, based on mapping literature review studies, there are 14 topics related to the influence of the LAR ratio on Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely: Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR, share price, amount of credit disbursement, intermediation level capability, Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR, Non Performing Loan/NPL, Murabahah financing, Musyarakah financing, Mudharabah financing, Price Earning Ratio/PER, Return On Assets/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE, Bank Return, and tax avoidance.

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